

СЎЗ САЊАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

5 ЖИЛД, 4 СОН

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

ТОМ 5, НОМЕР 4

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

VOLUME 5, ISSUE 4

СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА | INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

№4 (2022) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9297-2022-4>

Бош муҳаррир:

Тўхтасинов Илҳом

п.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Бош муҳаррир ўринбосари:

Главный редактор:

Тухтасинов Илхом

д.п.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Заместитель главного редактора:

Editor in Chief:

Tuhtasinov Ilhom

DSc. Professor (Uzbekistan)

Deputy Chief Editor

ТАҲРИРИЙ МАСЛАҲАТ КЕНГАШИ

Назаров Бахтиёр

академик. (Ўзбекистон)

Якуб Умарўғли

ф.ф.д., профессор (Туркия)

Алмаз Улви Биннатова

ф.ф.д., профессор (Озарбайжон)

Бокиева Гуландом

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Миннуллин Ким

ф.ф.д., профессор (Татаристон)

Махмудов Низомиддин

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Керимов Исмаил

ф.ф.д., профессор (Россия)

Жўраев Маматкул

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Куренов Рахиммаед

к.ф.н. (Туркменистон)

Кристофер Жеймс Форт

Мичиган университети (АҚШ)

Умархўжаев Мухтор

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Мирзаев Ибодулло

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Болтабоев Ҳамидулла

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Дўстмухаммедов Хуршид

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Лиходзиевский А.С.

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Сиддикова Ирода

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Шиукашвили Тамар

ф.ф.д. (Грузия)

Юсупов Ойбек

масбул котиб, доцент (Ўзбекистон)

РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ СОВЕТ

Назаров Бахтиёр

академик. (Узбекистан)

Якуб Умар оглы

д.ф.н., профессор (Туркия)

Алмаз Улви Биннатова

д.ф.н., профессор (Азербайджан)

Бакиева Гуландом

д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Миннуллин Ким

д.ф.н., профессор (Татарстан)

Махмудов Низомиддин

д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Керимов Исмаил

д.ф.н., профессор (Россия)

Джураев Маматкул

д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Куренов Рахыммаед

к.ф.н. (Туркменистан)

Кристофер Джеймс Форт

Университет Мичигана (США)

Умархаджаев Мухтар

д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Мирзаев Ибодулло

д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Балтабоев Ҳамидулла

д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Дустмухаммедов Хуршид

д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Лиходзиевский А.С.

д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Сиддикова Ирода

д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Шиукашвили Тамар

д.ф.н. (Грузия)

Юсупов Ойбек

отв. секретарь, доцент (Узбекистан)

EDITORIAL BOARD

Bakhtiyor Nazarov

academician. (Uzbekistan)

Yakub Umarogli

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Turkey)

Almaz Ulvi Binnatova

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Azerbaijan)

Bakieva Gulandom

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Minnulin Kim

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Tatarstan)

Mahmudov Nizomiddin

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Kerimov Ismail

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Russia)

Juraev Mamatkul

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Kurenov Rakhimmamed

Ph.D. Ass. Prof. (Turkmenistan)

Christopher James Fort

University of Michigan (USA)

Umarkhodjaev Mukhtar

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Mirzaev Ibodulla

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Boltaboev Hamidulla

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Dustmuhammedov Khurshid

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Lixodzievsky A.S.

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Siddiqova Iroda

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Shiukashvili Tamar

Doc. of philol. scien. (Georgia)

Yusupov Oybek

Ass. prof. (Uzbekistan) - Senior Secretary

PageMaker | Верстка | Саҳифаловчи: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz

ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,

улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz

Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,

Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz

Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

1. Elmurodova Gulrukh Karimalievna TOURISM TEXTS AND THEIR PRAGMALINGUISTIC FEATURES.....	5
2. Qahramon Eshboyev GRADUONIMIYA VA SINONIMIYANING O‘ZARO MUNOSABATI MASALASI XUSUSIDA.....	12
3. Райхонова Мухайё Мухаммадиевна ШЕЪРИЯТДА БАДИИЙ ТАСВИР УЙҒУНЛИГИ.....	16
4. Дилдора Юнус кизи Юсупова ЭВФЕМИЗМЫ В ПОЭЗИИ ХАЛИМЫ ХУДОЙБЕРДИЕВОЙ.....	23
5. Dilorom Nigmatovna Yuldasheva, Madina Ithom qizi Ro‘ziyeva LISON-TAFAKKUR-NUTQ MUNOSABATI – SUBSTANSIAL TILSHUNOSLIKNING BOSH MAVZUSI.....	29
6. Жаримбетова Толғанай Қурбанбаевна БАДИИЙ ХУЖЖАТЛИ ҚИССАЛАРДА ҚАХРАМОН ОБРАЗИНИ ЁРАТИШ МАҲОРАТИ.....	36
7. Назарова Иноятхон Бахтиёрхўжаевна МИЛЛИЙ ЭСТРАДА АКТЕРИ ВА УНИНГ НУТҚ МАҲОРАТИ.....	43
8. Ниязов Равшан Туракулович ДЕТЕКТИВ ЖАНР ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ ВА БАДИИЙ ЎЗИГА ХОСЛИГИ.....	49
9. Tajiboyev Botir Raximjonovich ASSOTSIATIV LUG‘ATLARNING YARATILISHIGA BIR NAZAR.....	56
10. Шеркулов Сардор Комилович ЗАМОНАВИЙ ЎЗБЕК АДАБИЁТИДА У.ФОЛЬКНЕР НАСРИ АНЪАНАЛАРИ.....	61
11. Yuldasheva Dilorom Nigmatovna, Gulamova Dilobar Imamkulovna EVFEMIZMLAR O‘QUVCHI NUTQ MADANIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRUVCHI OMIL SIFATIDA.....	67
12. Юсупова Дилдора Юнусовна ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННАЯ РЕЧЬ И МНОГОЗНАЧНОСТЬ.....	74
13. Abdurakhmanova Nargiza Nusratullayevna THE CONCEPT OF “INSTRUCTIVE DISCOURSE” IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK AND ITS METHODOLOGY....	81
14. Pхomova Umida Djamaliddinovna AMERIKA ADABIYOTIDA “O‘QITUVCHI” OBRAZINING BADIY TALQINI (BEL KAUFMANNING “PASTKI ZINADAN YUQORIGA” ASARI MISOLIDA).....	87
15. Наширова Дилноза ЎЗБЕК ТИЛИДА ЙЎНАЛМА ҲАРАКАТ ФЕЪЛЛАРИ ТИЗИМИ.....	92
16. Rasulova Soxiba Ulug‘bekovna WASHINGTON IRVING IJODIDA SATIRA VA YUMOR.....	98
17. G‘aybullayeva Xatira Muratdjanovna BADIY TARJIMADA LINGVOMADANIY TAHLILNING AHAMIYATI.....	107
18. Икрамова Азиза Аминовна ИҚБОЛ МИРЗОНИНГ “САМАРҚАНД САЙҚАЛИ” ШЕЪРИЙ ДРАМАСИДА СИНКРЕТИК ХУСУСИЯТЛАР.....	113
19. Abduxalimova Sarvinoxon THE CONCEPT AND CONTENT OF INTERCULTURAL DISCOURSE.....	119

20. Турсуной Эргашева СОЛИҚ ВА СОЛИҚҚА ТОРТИШ ЙЎНАЛИШИ МУТАХАССИСЛАРИГА ИНГЛИЗ ТИЛИНИ ЎҚИТИШНИНГ ЗАМОНАВИЙ УСУЛЛАРИ.....	125
21. Boboyorova Maftuna Raxmonovna INGLIZ TILIDA SO'Z YASALISHINING BA'ZI USULLARI VA USLUBLARI.....	130
22. Qilicheva Gulruh Narzullayevna GUSTAV FLOBERNING "SALAMBO" ROMANIDA INSON RUHIYATINING BADIY TALQINI.....	135
23. Rustamova Shahnoza Aripovna, Asadova Chehrangiz Salimovna, Boboyorova Maftuna Raxmonovna CHET TILI O'QITISH BO'YICHA BOSHLANG'ICH SINIF O'QUVCHILARINING O'Z-O'ZINI BAHOLANISH KOMPETENSIYASINI SHAKLLANTIRISH.....	139
24. Eshimova Sharofat Kenjaboyevna PERSONIFIKATSIYA ORQALI OBRAZNING YARATILISHI.....	146
25. Абдуллаева Нилуфар Насуллоевна ЛЕКЛЕЗИОНИНГ "ОЧЛИК РАҚСИ" РОМАНИДА ҚАҲРАМОНЛАР СИЙМОСИДА ЖАМИЯТ ҲАЁТИНИНГ ТАСВИРЛАНИШИ.....	152
26. Дилбар Холтемировна Ниязова БАДИИЙ МАТНДА ИЖОДКОРНИНГ СЎЗ ТАНЛАШ ВА ҚЎЛЛАШ МАҲОРАТИ.....	159
27. Наширова Дилноза ЎЗБЕК ТИЛИДА ЙЎНАЛИМА ҲАРАКАТ ФЕЪЛЛАРИ ТИЗИМИ.....	164
28. Usmanova Moxira Kenjayevna O'ZBEK TILIDA SO'ZLARINING TOVUSH ALMASHISHI NATIJASIDA SODDALASHISHGA UCHRAGAN BIRLIKLAR.....	175
29. Халида Йўлдашева БАДИИЙ МАТНДА ИЖТИМОИЙ ДЕЙКСИСГА ИШОРА ҚИЛУВЧИ ГРАММАТИК ВОСИТАЛАР.....	176
30. Хотамова Парвина Илхомовна ЎЗБЕК ТИЛИ ГАП ТАРКИБИДА КВАЛИКАТИВ ПОСЕССИВ СИНТАКСЕМА ВАРИАНТЛАРИ.....	182
31. Хотамова Парвина Илхомовна КВАЛИКАТИВ ПОСЕССИВ, ПОССЕСИВ ТОТАЛ, ПОСЕССИВ АГЕНТИВ СИНТАКСЕМАЛАР.....	185
32. Турымбетов Байрамбай Қонысбаевич Г. ЕСЕМУРАТОВА АСАРЛАРИДА ДАВР ҲАҚИҚАТИ ТАСВИРИ.....	189
33. Mirjalilova Madina Jamshid qizi FRAZEOLIGIK BIRLIKLAR LINGVOKULTUREMA SIFATIDA.....	194

Назарова Иноятхон Бахтиёрхўжаевна
Ўзбекистон Давлат Санъат ва Маданият Институтини
“Саҳна нутқи” кафедраси ўқитувчиси
3-босқич мустақил изланувчи (PhD)

МИЛЛИЙ ЭСТРАДА АКТЁРИ ВА УНИНГ НУТҚ МАҲОРАТИ

 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6775664>

АННОТАЦИЯ

Мақолада миллий эстраданинг ривожланиш жараёнида ўзбек актёрларининг ўрни ўзбек миллий эстрада санъатининг сўз жанрида ижод қилган, ўзига хос мактаб яратган, ўзбек кизиқчилиги, аския санъати ривожига катта ҳисса қўшган санъаткор Муҳиддин Дарвешов ва унинг шогирди актёр-қизиқ Рустам Ҳамроқулов ҳақида сўз боради. Актёрларнинг ижро қилган репертуарига тўхталиб, актёрлик ва саҳна нутқи маҳорати ўрганилади хулосалар қилинади.

Таянч сўзлар: кизиқчи, миллий эстрада, саҳна маданияти, латифа, монолог, аския.

Назарова Иноятхон Бахтиёрхўжаевна
Государственный институт искусств и культуры Узбекистана
Преподавателя кафедры «Сценической речи»
Независимый исследователь (PhD) 3-курс

АКТЕР НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ЭСТРАДЫ И ЕГО НАВЫК РЕЧИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассматривается Муҳиддин Дарвешов, художнике, творивший в жанре узбекского национального эстрадного искусства, создавший уникальную школу, внесший большой вклад в развитие узбекского интереса, искусства аския, и его ученик Рустам Ҳамроқулов. Ориентируясь на репертуар в исполнении актеров, изучается актерское мастерство и сценическая речь и делаются выводы.

Ключевые слова: юморист, национальная эстрада, сценическая культура, шутка, монолог, разговорные шутки и каламбуры.

Nazarova Inoyatkhon Bahtiyorhojayevna
State Institute of Arts and Culture of Uzbekistan
Lecturer of faculty chair "Scene speech"
Independent Researcher (PhD) 3-year

A NATIONAL POP ACTOR AND HIS SPEAKING SKILLS

ANNOTATION

The article looks at Muhiddin Darveshov, an artist who created in the genre of Uzbek national pop art, created a unique school, made a great contribution to the development of Uzbek interest, Askiya art, and his student Rustam Hamrokulov. Focusing on the repertoire performed by the actors, the acting and stage speech skills are studied and conclusions are drawn.

Keywords: humorist, national stage, sthenic culture, joke, monologue, colloquial jokes and puns.

“Askiya is an independent genre of Uzbek folklore, which is closely related to human activity, mood, daily life, relationships, emotions, creative thinking” [1.1]. The askiya genre plays an important role in educating people as a person with a delicate temperament, cheerful nature, cheerfulness, extreme taste, intelligence and sensitivity.

The word "askiya" is derived from the Arabic word "zakiy", which means "eloquent", "intelligent", "sharp-minded". People who perform askiya are called askiya performers, askiyachi. The history of askiya goes back a long way. According to written historical sources, askiya was widespread in the XV-XVII centuries. Poet and scholar Zayniddin Wasifi writes that Askiya was widespread in Herat and named Mawlana Abdulvose Munshi as the most talented among dozens of skilled askiya performers.[2.261] Askiya has such types as payrov, rhyme, radif, total, imitated, bahri byte, nonsense, “gulmisiz, jambilmisiz, rayhonmisiz”, sweetness, legend, rabbi, nickname, exaggeration, kesatik, lof, chiston, etc.

Every nation has a sense of humor, an argument, an asceticism. The difference between the Uzbek askiya and the ordinary jokes of other peoples is that it has risen to the level of art. Askiya is a kind of Uzbek folklore, an integral part of the people's interest, a common spectacle.[3.105]

Rasul Muhammadiev, Doctor of Philology, was the first scientist to study the art of Askiya. At his initiative, three Askiya expeditions were organized. In the process, the askiya performers were brought together, competitions were organized, conversations and walks were recorded. Eventually, on the basis of this expedition, in 1970, the collection "Askiya" was published and a film of the same name was made.

Linguist H. Razzokov, evaluating the artists working in the Askiya genre, said that askiya people revive the Uzbek language in different colors by using homonyms, synonyms, antonyms, paying attention to figurative words, and in some cases by substituting or deliberately distorting sounds.[2.264]

Askiya is the art of knowing the meanings of words and sentences (own and portable meanings) with subtle comprehension, quick and sharp intellect, ingenuity, wit, intelligence, comprehension, answering questions appropriately, avoidance, word games. One of its main features is responsiveness. The one who performs askiya is firmly committed to grace and kindness. For this reason, the performer must be able to find words that have a diverse, deep and broad meaning that is directly related to the topic, and must work tirelessly on himself. To do this, a participant in the askiya must have a rich life experience, a sharp mind, a thorough knowledge of various aspects of human activity, and social life, as well as the richness of the Uzbek language. Only then will he become an artist who conveys the true meaning of the word to the audience and gives it a sense of humor. Researchers have often said that if an interested person considers himself an artist, then he should strictly adhere to the culture of the stage. It is gratifying that today the number of young artists interested in the art of hobby is growing. Here it is necessary to observe the art of teachers in adhering to the etiquette, stage and speech culture on stage. After all, this serves as a great lesson for young people.

A curious person should have a perfect knowledge of the character, history and way of life of the people. After all, when he takes the image, the reality, and the language from the people, it is no doubt an inappropriate remark, that he himself is destined to be the target of laughter. The reasons why Askiya laughter nights and walks are held in the mahalla guzars are also due to its popularity. As the thoughts of the people are sung in delicate veils, the expressions in them are spoken quickly. [4.1]

Yusufjon Qiziq Shakarjanov from Margilan, a farmer from Bachkir village Shernazarov, Erka Qori Karimov, Mamayunus Tillaboev, Mamatkholik Masodikov, Tursunbuva Aminov, Abdulhay Makhsum Kozokov from Andijan, Mullamamat Buva, Jurahon Tashmanov, Ushan Akbar, Usmonov, Gurahon are greatly respected in the history of Uzbek askiya. Along with Yusufjon Qiziq Shakarjanov, in the first half of the XX century and in 1950-60, dozens of people like Ohunjon Qiziq Huzurjonov aka Bukhar Zokirov have been serving the people by developing the traditions of ancient art in accordance with the needs of the new era.[5.7] When they came on stage, involuntarily smiles ran down the faces of the people. Feeling the responsibility of the word, not wasting it for nonsense, but knowingly using it, were important rules in the path of creativity of the above-named enthusiasts. In the course of his research, Professor M. Kadyrov deeply studies the work of Muhiddin Kizik and gives positive opinions.[6.213] "..... it is noteworthy that Muhiddin Darveshov was a leading comedian in 1970-80." [5.7] Although M. Darveshev actually graduated from the Samarkand Agricultural Institute, he followed Tesha Qiziq Kamilov and Ohunjon Qiziq Huzurjanov and entered the art of curiosity. The late Rustam Hamrokulov, Hojiboy Tadjibayev, Bahodir Shokirov, Abdulla Akbarov, Abdurahmon Siddikov consider Muhiddin Qiziq Darveshev as their teacher.

Muhiddin Darvesh was able to attract the attention of the audience with his use of words in different tones, effective use of elements of dialect, his ability to clearly and vividly embody the image of the person he creates or narrates in front of the audience through his mimics, hand gestures and words. The audience enjoyed the artist's askiya and laughed heartily. Such spiritual rest, of course, gave them the energy to make their future work day, and life in general, more productive. "Because he was a treasure, he invented a new story, a new" . [6.217]

Muhiddin sought to use words effectively when narrating an interesting event or creating an image, while at the same time not using excessive gestures to distract the viewer. When the name of this master of words is mentioned, in the eyes of our people there is an image of an artist wearing a white skullcap. Our older compatriots remember this curious person, who became a part of their youth, with a smile on their faces. "Although he did not choose traditional comedies and parables and focused only on the forms of the story, he was able to instantly take on the image of each series's protagonist, weighing and tapping words, moving his eyes, eyebrows, moving his hands, even in moments. Muhiddin's interesting work is one of the most interesting aspects of his work. There are many reasons why the interesting name of Muhiddin, a true son of the Uzbek people, has always lived in the hearts of generations over the years.

First of all, the repertoire of this artist is very rich, he created in the genres of comedy-story, anecdote and hangoma. He created a series of programs because he connected them in his performances. For example, narrating stories from his own life and the life of the teacher's hobbies, performing jokes and anecdotes, Abduraim dovdirdir and Mamaraim's male adventures, telling anecdotes from life events.

Muhiddin Darveshov and the stage variety that came through him have expanded and enriched the range of television comedy programs. After all, Darveshov gave the Uzbek variety to the stage variety due to the originality of the school of interest in the Fergana Valley. Although his work was not regularly used on television in certain shows, his participation in the amateur roundtables, as well as the provision of some comics, hangomas and askiyas, increased his interest in him and his work. [7.98]

The entertainer is not only a fun professional who makes people laugh, but also an artist who sees and analyzes the problems of the time in which he lives, the various flaws, and observes their solutions. Muhiddin Darveshev was a master of humor in his repertoire.

The artist was one of the first to pay attention to the topic of gender equality, which is still relevant today in our time, 40-45 years ago, and ridicules the special treatment of the opposite gender.

In the course of our research, we witnessed that the amateur Youtub.com (https://salda.ws/video.php?id=N-A6o4Cv_pQ) devoted a great deal of space to the above topic in the 1981 concert program posted on the world wide web.

M. Kadyrov criticized the shortcomings of young amateurs in their speech and said that they do not allow them to speak fluently, to digest stories and words. He says that he worked tirelessly on

it and later gained self-confidence. However, he stressed that one should not go on stage without seeing the master.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the work of Muhiddin Qiziq Darveshov made a significant contribution to the creation of national pop music, the development of the genre of pop art. The actor was able to captivate the audience with his eloquence, strong speech culture, additional acting skills and wit, and created a school for the next generation of artists to show the culture of speech on stage with his performances

Rustam Hamrokulov, one of Muhiddin Darveshev's talented students, lived a short life. Nevertheless, he managed to leave a worthy mark on himself in life and art.

The work of Rustam Hamrokulov, like Muhiddin Darveshov, served to develop originality in the performance of the new era.[7.101]

Honored Worker of the Republic of Uzbekistan Rustam Hamrokulov was born on August 10, 1953 in the village of Sang, Pop district, Namangan region. Although the members of this family were ordinary people and engaged in various occupations to make a living, art was no stranger to this household.

According to the wife of the master of words Mavluda Hamrokulova, "R. Hamrokulov's grandfather - Hamroqul buva was an art lover, although he was originally a potter. In the past, representatives of three or four households used to gather in one place and pick cotton. Hamroqul bobo used to tell funny jokes and instructive stories so that the neighbors would not be bored. R. Hamrokulov's father was also a very interesting person. He could find the words, even though he was short." [8.1]

Due to the family environment, Rustam grows up to be a talkative, like his grandfather and father, able to use the right word in his place, eager to lift the mood of others through humor.

After graduating from high school, his love and passion for art led the future master of speech to the capital. It is noteworthy that R. Hamrokulov in the entrance exams to the department of drama acting of the Institute of Theater and Art attracts the attention of teachers through a single scene.

After R. Hamrokulov joined the army and served in the army, he started working at the Alisher Navoi Musical Drama Theater in Pop district. The talented actor plays roles in a number of musical performances, which brings him great fame, especially the image of Efendi in the play "Khoja Nasriddin".

In those years, on the eve of the cotton season, artists did not come from "Ishkom", and in order to raise the mood of cotton growers and pickers, respectively, held mobile concert programs in all villages and districts. Rustam aka was tasked to show small pieces from the play "Khoja Nasriddin". Because of these performances, he has entered a world of self-interest.[8.1] If we compare this aspect with Muhiddin Darveshov's, on the contrary, "Kokand also worked in the People's Theater and played some funny roles. But working on the basis of the author's text did not suit him. [6.216] The interest has become so rare and connected with the inner pains of man that in order to reveal and develop it, man must be born curious.

Thus, due to the situation and the times, as well as the love of humor by nature, Rustam Hamrokulov, although originally a theater actor, began to be known among the people as a master of words.

The versatile artist was a serious and extremely demanding person outside of the stage (in life). He was an artist who was especially careful about the issue of speech, the ethics of the stage.

No matter how much Rustam Aka was loved and respected by the fans, he was excited in front of them. At times like these, his spouse would tell him, "Why are you so excited? Isn't this your first time on stage?" The actor even burned it. "The artist's lack of excitement is a sign that his work is dead," he said.

Mavluda Hamrokulova was the first listener of the famous master of words, who memorized the scripts and jokes. After the kids fell asleep, they would stand in front of the window and perform scenes. She would sit on the sidelines and correct his mistakes. Rustam aka would say, "You are a philologist, pay attention to which word I mispronounce and which one I misuse." [8.1]

Hamrokulov was an artist who showed his unique side in combining the style of folk performance with modern stage pop laughter. We can see that Rustam Hamrokulov Muhiddin is interesting as he appeared in new faces in moments, and based on the image, he paid attention to the ability to express the individuality of the voice, manner, body. [7.101] There are almost all the themes in his repertoire, such as "Autobase", "Army", "Family relations". Of course, in the formation of any amateur or pop actor, there is also the influence of the region where he was born and raised. The reason is that each region of the country has its own dialect, which is clearly reflected in the speech of the actor. Only an actor who is able to connect the dialect of this or that region to his creative repertoire can succeed in his career. At the same time, the pronunciation of the actor and the dialect he uses should not interfere with the effectiveness and interest of the subject, but rather serve to further enrich and enhance the spectacle. The process of research shows that Rustam Hamrokulov was able to use the dialect of the valley in its place and effectively.

In "The Incident at the Rare Goods Store"[9], the master of the word interprets the role of a buyer who comes to the store in a hurry to buy an atlas, and his student a salesman. Rustam Khamrokulov embodies the image of a buyer in the image of a woman, polite and revengeful. The character is flattering at the beginning of the story, speaking slowly and sparingly, but when things don't turn out as he expected, he behaves like a mysterious person in a high position, rides a jealous horse and involuntarily makes the listener laugh by giving the seller various unreasonable tasks. R. Hamrokulov is a simple, sincere, cunning and deceitful image of the buyer due to his beautiful speaking ability, the ability to color certain letters in different tones, to speak in a low, mysterious voice when necessary, in a high tone when the situation requires it. interprets as a person. From the comedy it can be concluded that not everyone in life actually looks the same or behaves the way he or she does. In Rustam Hamrokulov's repertoire, which consists of various colorful themes, one can find many comedies and scenes on the theme of alcohol. While addressing the subject, the master of the word is in no hurry to criticize the viewer for the negative aspects of this flaw. Perhaps he tries to express his attitude on the issue through some philosophical, somewhat humorous views. For example, R. Hamrokulov, who listened to a comedy made by a road patrol officer to stop a person who endangered his family by driving under the influence of alcohol and used a Japanese device to prove that he drank, portrays the author, a drunk driver, a road patrol officer and a Japanese cameraman. The fact that even a technical miracle fails in the face of the drunken driver's ingenuity makes the listener laugh. However, the astute viewer is well aware that through this number, the master of words is hinting that alcohol poses a serious threat to the fate of families. Only someone who has listened to this comedy over and over again will realize that behind the sweet laughter lies the bitter truth.

The themes chosen by the actor are taken from the lives of ordinary people, they are very popular and sincere. It is also reflected in the actor's deep culture, respect for the audience, norms and intelligence in the choice of subject. In the comedy "Children from the Army" Hamrokulov gives a special color and tone to the words of the author. It describes the appearance, manners, and culture of behavior of young men who went and did not go to the army.

As he rides his motorbike to the head of the village, some of the young men who do not know what to do with him, the involuntary listener sees the noisy, dusty village streets and the disgruntled image of the villagers. The word master makes the noise of the guy coming out of the engine, the noisy, unpleasant sound coming out of the engine, so convincingly that it sounds as if it is ringing under your ear.

The master of the Word expresses in a festive, uplifting tone that the silence and the environment have become more beautiful after the plan to repel the bully has been implemented, and the listener is convinced of this. In front of us is a wonderful view of a peaceful village, the image of a simple and sincere villager living in peace and tranquility. The power of the artistic word must be in fact the same.

The Uzbek national pop art we are talking about has such talented representatives as Yusufjon Qiziq, Muhiddin Darveshov, Saib Khodjaev, Ergash Karimov, Rustam Hamrokulov. It is the task of our young scientists to study their innate pure fluent speech, the ability to improvise.

References:

1. <http://ich.uz/uz/ich-of-uzbekistan/elements-included/92-askiya>
2. Razzoqov H. Ўзбек халқ оғзаки поэтик ижоди.- (Uzbek folk oral poetic creativity), Tashkent.: Teacher. 1980. P. 261-264.
3. Kadyrov O`zbek xalq tomosha san`ati (Uzbek folk art), Tashkent.: Teacher, 1981. P. 105.
4. <https://azon.uz/content/views/biz-nega-kulayapmiz-yohud-manaviyat> .
5. Sh.Hamidova, Estrada teatri va uning janrlari (Variety of theater and its genres) textbook.Toshkent.2009. P.6-7
6. Kadyrov M O`zbek teatr tarixi (History of Uzbek theater), Tashkent.: Creative world. 2003. P. 213-16-217.
7. Sulstonov O. Ўзбекистон телевидениесида кулги санъати (The art of comedy on Uzbek television), Tashkent.: Gafur Ghulam Publishing House. 2005. P. 98-101.
8. Муродова Н. Рустам Ҳамроқуловни ёд этиб: «Ўлим уни шошириб қўйганди!». <https://www.xabar.uz/madaniyat/olim-uni-shoshirib-qoYGandi> 2018 йил. 3май
9. Yusupov O. CHARACTER EXPRESSION IN LITERARY TRANSLATION //Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 4.
10. Yusupov O. et al. Phraseological Units with Colour Designation Component as a Means of Reflecting the Self-Consciousness of the English People //LINGUISTICA ANTVERPIENSIA. – 2021. – С. 719-731.
11. Yusupov, O. N. "Subtleties Of Literary Translation."İlköğretim Online (İOO)-Elementary Education Online 4.4 (2021): 1987-1991.
12. <https://m.youtube.com/watch?v=cxRfZih3dpc>

СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

5 ЖИЛД, 4 СОН

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

ТОМ 5, НОМЕР 4

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

VOLUME 5, ISSUE 4

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000